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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT OF THE CLASSIFICATION OF SCREW
RELATIONAL DRUMS**¹Alexey Marchenko¹Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilin, Kalinina str. 13, Krasnodar 350044, Russia.**Article Received:** June 2019**Accepted:** July 2019**Published:** August 2019**Abstract:**

The article presents, developed by the author, the classification of working bodies of machines in the form of screw relational drums. The results of the research are summarized in tables 1-9, which presents the design of the currently known screw relational drums, providing, in a horizontal arrangement, the movement of bulk materials (feed components) and intensifying interactions with each other and with the wall of the screw relational drums, which expands technological capabilities and reduces the size of the equipment and their mass [1, 2, 3, 4]. The approbation of the classification of screw relational drums was carried out, with the help of which the original designs of screw relational drums were created, the novelty of which was confirmed by 87 patents of the Russian Federation for inventions, 40 of them – feed preparation devices: 2358620, 2372817, 1237818, 2373809, 2373810, 2376913, 2385663, 2385664, 2457746, 2467670, 2540583, 2541663, 2548889, 2548888, 2548890, 2548187, 2548184, 2546180, 2551147, 2555814, 2556063, 2564487, 2564491, 2565733, 2565730, 2566996, 2566991, 2566657, 2566669, 2572208, 2569954, 2570719, 2572208, 2579209, 2594883, 2594994, 2594993, 2600008, 2600009 2603040.

Keywords: relational, helical drum, classification, helical lines, smooth, broken, spiral.**Corresponding author:****Alexey Marchenko,**Kuban State Agrarian University named after I.T. Trubilin,
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INTRODUCTION:

An analysis of the state and prospects for the development of technologies and equipment for the preparation of feeds allowed us to conclude that in order to increase productivity, feed preparation machines with working bodies are needed in which the feed preparation process would be carried out not only with the volumetric interaction of the particles of the feed components, but also the process itself preparation of feed would occur during the transportation of particles of feed components in an unoriented state in the working organ not a feed preparation machine from loading to unloading.

The aim of this work is to create a progressive process for the preparation of feed, based on the use of continuous machines, with working bodies in the form of screw relational drums.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The combination of transport and technological functions is ensured by the installation of flat, curvilinear or rod elements along the perimeter of the working body of the feed preparation machines, multidirectional with respect to helical lines along its perimeter, as well as devices with a complex surface around the perimeter and with tension springs fixed inside, in which compound screw effect. We call such aggregates and devices with different configurations relational, as this is a general term that takes in conventions, similarities, relativity from certain conditions, forms and purposes.

Therefore, they are called by us screw relational drums.

Changing the layout of flat, curvilinear or rod elements in screw relational drums allows you to control the complex spatial motion of the flows of

particles of the components of the feed, i.e. increase or decrease the performance of feed preparation or regulate the quality of feed.

To impart low-frequency vibrations with a large amplitude of 15-1000 mm or more to the components of the feed components, the spatial shape of the helical relational drums is formed by mounting flat, curvilinear or rod elements around their perimeter. As a result of the studies, a classification of relational screw drums was created (Figure 1) and Figure 2-10 which show the designs of: screw relational drums:

- cylindrical (RC) - conventional cylindrical shape;
- conical (RK) - conditionally conical shape;
- convex (RVP) —conditionally convex in shape;
- concave (RVG) - conditionally concave shape;
- rod (RP) - mounted from helical rods;
- annular (RKO) —conditionally annular in shape with a conditionally broken outer surface, along the perimeter of which broken or curved helical lines are located.
- spiral (RS) - conditionally spiral form;
- square (RCA) of course square shape;

Each of these types of relational screw drums includes 7 classes located along the perimeter:

- 1st class - continuous broken lines;
- 2nd class - in separate sections of broken helical lines rotated relative to each other;
- 3rd class - directed towards each other by broken helical lines of the same pitch;
- 4th class - with four broken helical lines and two broken helical lines of the opposite direction;
- 5th class - three helical directional from loading to unloading, and two broken helical lines of the opposite direction;
- 6th class - broken lines of the same direction;
- 7th class - smooth helical lines in one direction.

Figure 1: Classification of screw relational drums

Moreover, the classes of all types of screw relational drums can differ in the number of helical or zigzag lines, for example:

- subclass a - three (n);
- subclass b - four ($n + 1$);
- subclass b - five ($n + 2$);
- subclass g - six ($n + 3$), etc.

We will try to imagine the movement of the components of the feed, for example, peas (within the material point). In screw relational drums of the 4th and 5th classes, these movements are determined by the ratio of the screw parameters of the step and the number of approaches. In screw relational drums of

the 6th and 7th classes, the direction of axial movement is uniquely determined. In screw relational drums of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd classes, if you think completely abstractly, there should not be axial movement. Therefore, when installing feed preparation machines with screw relational drums of the 1st, 2nd and 3rd classes, a slight ($3-7^\circ$) slope is created so that due to the acting gravity force to create movements of the feed components in the right direction, to a certain extent, this is facilitated by the intake of feed components, and the multidirectionality of the screw surfaces creates a mixing effect.

Figure 2: Classification of cylindrical drums of screw relational drums

Figure 3: Classification of cylindrical drums of helical relational drums

Figure 4: Classification of conical helical relational drums

Figure 5: Classification of conical helical relational drums

class	subclass	Front views and visual image	
1	1		
3	1		
7	1		
	2		

Figure 6: Classification of convex helical relational drums

класс	подкласс	Виды спереди и сбоку	
1	1		

Figure 7: Classification of concave helical relational drums

class	subclass	Isometric view and cut	
3	1		
4	1		
5	1		

Figure 8: Classification of ring helical relational drums

Figure 9: Classification of spiral helical relational drums

Figure 10 Classification of square helical relational drums

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Based on the results of the research, a classification of screw relational drums has been created, with the help of which, like the periodic table, it is possible to find new original designs of screw relational drums using the methods known in the classification using descriptive geometry and engineering graphics using the Compass-3D software package.

CONCLUSION:

The article not only presents the author's classification of screw relational drums, but also outlines ways to optimize the dimensions of the working bodies of equipment in the form of screw relational drums. Varieties of types of screw

relational drums, their classes and subclasses are shown, which allow to select the working body of the feed preparation machine with the given parameters according to the characteristics of the feeds, and thus solve the problem of optimizing the designs of feed preparation machines as a whole.

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